

Stability Constants of Phenanthraquinone Monothiosemicarbazone Complexes with Bivalent Metal Ions

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Stability constants of complexes formed by Mg(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) with phenanthraquinone monothiosemicarbazone have been determined *pH*-metrically at $20 \pm 1^\circ$ in 75% (v/v) dioxane and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength. The values of $S_{m \pm n}$ have also been calculated. The order of stability constants was found to be Mg(II) < Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Pb(II) < Zn(II) < Cd(II) < Fe(II). Thermodynamic stabilization energies (δH) of the complexes have also been calculated and the order is Ni(II) > Co(II) > Fe(II).

In the present study stability constants of bivalent metal complexes of phenanthraquinone monothiosemicarbazone (PTS) have been determined potentiometrically. Thermodynamic stabilization energies have also been calculated.

Experimental

Phenanthraquinone monothiosemicarbazone (PTS) has been synthesized by refluxing equimolar amounts of phenanthraquinone and thiosemicarbazide in minimum amount of methanol for 3 hr. The hot solution was filtered. Red crystals formed on cooling were recrystallised from methanol (m.p. 191-193°). The purity of the PTS was checked by thin layer chromatography and elemental analysis. PTS acts as bidentate ligand by coordinating through phenolic oxygen and hydrazine nitrogen atom but it may coordinate through sulphur as well.

Solution of the ligand was prepared in purified dioxane¹. All the metal ion solutions were prepared by dissolving their nitrates or sulphates (B.D.H., AnalaR) and were standardized by standard methods. 0.05M solution of tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck) in 75% aqueous dioxane (v/v), standardized with standard solution of oxalic acid was used as the titrant. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. All other reagents were prepared from A.R. grade chemicals. An Ecil digital pH meter (model PH5651) with a combined electrode of 0-14 pH range was used for pH measurements. The pH meter was standardized with potassium

hydrogen phthalate and phosphate buffers. Titrations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere at $20 \pm 1^\circ$.

\bar{n} and *pL* values were determined following the method of Bjerrum and Calvin as adapted by Irving and Rossotti². The following solutions (total volume 20 ml) were titrated against 0.05M TMAH solution in 75% dioxane (v/v) maintaining the desired temperature with an accuracy of $\pm 1^\circ$. Requisite amount of NaClO₄ was added to maintain the ionic strength at 0.1M.

- (i) 0.8 ml HClO₄ (0.02 M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0 M) + 0.25 ml K₂SO₄ or KNO₃ (0.02 M) + 2.95 ml H₂O + 15.0 ml dioxane.
- (ii) 0.8 ml HClO₄ (0.02 M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0 M) + 0.25 ml K₂SO₄ or KNO₃ (0.02 M) + 2.95 ml H₂O + 15.0 ml PTS ($3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$) in dioxane.
- (iii) 0.8 ml HClO₄ (0.02 M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0 M) + 0.25 ml of metal nitrate or sulphate (0.02 M) + 2.95 ml H₂O + 15.0 ml PTS ($3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$) in dioxane.

In all the cases corrections for change in volumes on mixing dioxane and aqueous solution (total volume = 19.67 ml, instead of mixing dioxane and water) as well as change in volume taking place during the course of titrations, have been made.

Results and Discussion

It has been found by tlc of a sample of titration solution, taken from time to time that PTS does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. PTS has phenolic (OH) group which takes part in chelation and the proton (asterisk marked) is replaced by metal ion during complexation. The number of dissociated protons attached to each ligand molecule is one because only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation. The value of pK_a determined from the plot $[\bar{n}_H / (1 - \bar{n}_H)]$ vs pH has been found to be 11.4.

β_n values have been calculated from the values of \bar{n} and pL by weighted least square method of Sullivan *et al*⁵. S_{min} has also been calculated according with Sullivan *et al*⁵, which have the same significance as χ^2 , with k degrees of freedom.

The values of stability constants thus obtained have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL CHELATES WITH PTS ($\mu = 0.1$ at $20 \pm 1^\circ$)

Cation	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	log K_3	log β_3	S_{min}
Mg(II)	6.99	—	—	—	—	1.3355
Mn(II)	7.26	—	—	—	—	0.4448
Co(II)	7.46	6.93	14.40	7.12	21.52	0.7785
Ni(II)	8.38	6.42	14.80	8.16	22.96	0.2363
Pb(II)	8.45	10.45	18.90	8.18	27.08	0.5341
Zn(II)	9.49	7.33	16.82	9.33	26.15	0.4748
Cd(II)	9.77	8.43	18.20	9.31	27.51	0.6396
Fe(II)	10.68	—	—	—	—	1.1343

The order of increasing stability constants of the metal complexes is Mg(II) < Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Pb(II) < Zn(II) < Cd(II) < Fe(II). Except iron(II) complex, the order is in agreement with the order of stability constants reported by Irving and Williams⁴ and Mellor and Maley⁵. The anomalous behaviour of Fe(II) is theoretically anticipated due to the resonance stabilization energy of Fe(II) complexes when coordinated with a ligand having an aromatic ring. The anomalous behaviour of iron(II) is also expected theoretically⁶. The order of log K_2 and log K_3 in case of lead(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes is in conformity with the order reported by other workers⁷⁻¹⁰.

TABLE 2—CALCULATION OF STABILIZATION ENERGIES (δH) FOR THE CHELATES OF PTS ($\mu = 0.1$ M, Temp. = 293 K)

	Mn ²⁺	Fe ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
log β_1	7.26	10.68	7.46	8.38	9.49
ΔG	40.75	59.59	41.87	47.04	53.27
ΔG_R	—	19.20	1.12	6.29	12.52
H^{2+}	2734	2834	2914	2993	2930
ΔH_H	—	109	180	259	196
ΔH_L	—	128.20	181.12	265.29	208.52
$[(n-5)/5]E_r$	—	41.70	83.41	125.11	208.52
δH	—	86.50	97.71	140.18	—

The free energy change (ΔG) and stabilization energy (δH) have been calculated from log K_1 according to the method described by George and McClure¹¹. The values obtained are given in Table 2. The order of δH is Fe(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II), which is in agreement with the conclusions reached from ligand field theory.

The E_r (Mn-Zn) value has been found to be 208.52 kJ/mole which is of the same order as observed for many other ligands which coordinate to the metal ion through one nitrogen and one oxygen atom. Further, the values of δH observed for Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes are of such order as to suggest the participation of one nitrogen and one oxygen in coordination. This indicates that the metal ions are bound to the ligand molecule through the oxygen and one nitrogen atom.

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